

MODERN STELLAR ASTRONOMY

 Characteristics of the brown dwarf population
in the vicinity of the Sun

 E.S. Postnikova,¹ M.D. Sizova,¹ T. Bugra-Keskin,² N.V. Chupina,¹ and S.V. Vereshchagin¹
¹*Institute of Astronomy of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Moscow, 119017 Russia*
²*Physics Department, Lomonosov Moscow State University, Moscow, 119991 Russia*
Sternberg Astronomical Institute, Lomonosov Moscow State University, Moscow, 119234 Russia
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Based on the catalog ([5], $r < 10$ pc from the Sun), a list of brown dwarfs (BDs) was compiled for which it was possible to find components of spatial coordinates and velocity ($n = 13$). Within the framework of the classical model of the Galaxy, numerical calculations of the orbits of BDs from our list were carried out. The distribution by orbital eccentricity (e) turned out to be on a narrow interval, which indicates a small spread in the ages of BDs. An exception is Gaia EDR3 ID 1589250088362827776, the kinematics of which ($e = 4.1$) indicates that it may belong to the halo. The distribution by Z_{max} showed that the BDs from our list are part of the population of the “thin” disk with $Z_{max} < 600$ pc.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Brown dwarfs (BDs) are objects with masses in the range from 0.012 [1, 2] to 0.0767 [3, 4] M_{\odot} , or, respectively, from 12.57 to 80.35 MJ. They undergo thermonuclear fusion reactions on the nuclei of light elements (deuterium, lithium, beryllium, boron). After the reserves of light element nuclei are exhausted, thermonuclear reactions cease, after which BD cool relatively quickly, turning into planets.

In [5] used Gaia EDR3 parallaxes [6] to census objects within 10 pc. The catalog is supplemented with objects not included in Gaia EDR3 to obtain a complete census out to 10 pc, including bright stars, close binaries, brown dwarfs, and exoplanets. The catalog is a compilation of a query in the SIMBAD database for all objects with parallax greater than 100 mas using a set of identifications, measurements, and bibliography. BDs with recent parallax measurements not yet in SIMBAD and exoplanets verified by the authors of the catalog are also added. The catalog contains 541 objects, including BDs and exoplanets in 339 systems located within 10 pc of the Sun. All stars (and BDs) have parallax and proper motion measurements, allowing their tangential velocity, VT, to be calculated. In addition, Gaia DR3 and [7] provides radial velocities for some stars, resulting in 309 stars with full kinematics in the 10 pc sample.

2. DATA

Our list of BDs from [5] is formed by objects for which ObjType='BD' (here and below the names of the parameters are from the original catalog) and includes $n = 97$. Of these, 6 pairs of objects have 2

rows in catalog (are double), while the astrometry in the catalog is the same, the photometry is different, Table 1. From these pairs, we left one star each, see Table 1. In total, 91 BDs remained in our sample. Note that a BD is not a star, it is a substellar object.

Figure 1. Distribution of brown dwarfs in our list in space. The orange sphere in the center represents the Sun. Labeled with Gaia ID.

Fig. 1 shows the distribution of BD (our list) in the solar neighborhood in the Cartesian coordinate system. Note the fairly uniform space distribution of BD. A rectangular galactic heliocentric coordinate system is used, in which the X axis is directed toward the Galactic Center ($l = 0^\circ$, $b = 0^\circ$), the Y axis is in the direction of the Galactic rotation ($l = 90^\circ$, $b = 0^\circ$), and the Z axis is toward the North Pole of the Galaxy ($b = 90^\circ$). The same coordinate system is further ap-

Table 1. Gaia star pairs and the criteria by which one star from the pair was left in the sample.

Name	Selection criteria
Luhman 16	Taken star with G from GEDR3
eps Ind	Taken star with G from GEDR3
2MASS J14162408+1348263	Taken star with G from GEDR3
WISE J121756.90+162640.8	Taken star for which J, H, K are known
WISEPA J045853.89+643452.9	Two identical records, one deleted
CWISE J061741.79+194512.8	Taken star with GCode=10 (G derived from spectral type)

Figure 2. The left panel shows the PM diagram. Stars with kinematics different from the average are marked in green (single) and blue (binary). It is also possible that some of these objects are binary, and this can distort the PM due to orbital motion. The right panel shows the dependence of the relative parallax error on Gmag. All stars have a relative parallax error not exceeding 1%.

plied for spatial velocities.

The proper motion (PM) diagram for $n = 91$ BDs in our list, presented in Fig. 2, shows that some BDs have PM components that differ significantly from the average value. These BDs may have kinematics similar to halo objects. The PM measurement errors are much smaller than the radial velocity errors.

Figure 3. Diagram of the position of the apices in the galactic coordinate system of stars with RV ($n = 309$) in the catalog [11] (blue dots) and 24 BD (red stars).

It is known that the classical formula for determining the distance of a star from the Sun through parallax ($r = 1/\omega$) can give large errors with inaccurate parallaxes. To check the reliability of using the distance, we constructed a diagram "relative parallax er-

ror - Gmag", shown in Fig. 2. As can be seen from Fig. 2, the parallax errors of the BDs of our list do not exceed 1%. This allows us to confidently use the classical formula to determine the distance from the Sun.

3. APEX DIAGRAM

Fig. 3 shows the apex diagram [8] of the stars in our list. A number of values deviating from the average are noticeable. For these stars, the radial velocity error significantly exceeds the value itself. Possible reasons for the deviation are discussed in this section.

The star EGGR 290 (G 99-47, GJ 1087, Gaia EDR3 1589250088362827776) in Fig. 3 possibly a white dwarf [9] with a suspiciously large $RV = -177 \pm 197$ km s^{-1} . RV was obtained as part of the SDSS-III study. The measurement accuracy is up to 200 ms^{-1} [10]. The high radial velocity is confirmed by another study based on the study of the properties of cold BDs and a comparison of various data from SDSS and Gaia, according to which the velocity is estimated at -336.898 km s^{-1} [11].

4. BINARY SYSTEMS

We found five BDs from our list in the WDS catalog [12], Table 2. Knowledge of the binarity allowed us to take into account their influence on the overall picture of the kinematics of the stars from our list, naturally, by giving less weight to the data of their orbital calculations, which we perform in the next section to determine which subsystem each of the BDs belongs to. This is due to the possible influence of the orbital motion velocity on the spatial velocity of the star. Table 2 shows the WDS numbers found for the BDs of our list and the parameters calculated by us.

5. NUMERICAL CALCULATION OF ORBITS

We performed numerical calculations of the BDs orbits using the galpy package [13]. The integration time is 500 Myr ago. 10,000 steps were calculated. The integration method is Runge-Kutta of the 4th order. The classical three-component model of the Galaxy MWP2014 was used. The kinematics of Gaia EDR3 ID 1589250088362827776 indicates that it may belong to the halo of the Galaxy due to its fairly elongated orbit ($e = 0.41$) and the height to which it rises relative to the disk $Z_{max} = 4.34$ kpc. It can be assumed that this object was once part of a break up binary star. However, for a more accurate assessment of its belonging to the Galaxy subsystem, reliable data on its chemical composition are needed. The eccentricity of a star's orbit around the Galactic Center and its age are related as follows [14]: old stars move in highly elongated orbits ($e > 0.5$), while young stars revolve around the Galactic center in orbits close to circular (for most of them, $e < 0.2 \sim 0.3$). For 13 BDs the radial velocities were found, we calculated the orbital eccentricities (e) and the maximum value of the orbital Z-coordinate (Z_{max}). The obtained values are presented in Table 3. To estimate the ages of the BDs in our list, we constructed the distribution of orbits by eccentricity, see Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 shows the relationship between the orbital eccentricity and the belonging of objects to different stellar subsystems of the Galaxy. The basis of the figure is taken from the paper by [14], where the orbital parameters of a large number of stars from Gaia DR2 were analyzed and the boundaries between the thin disc, thick disc and halo in the " $e \sim Z_{max}$ " plane (eccentricity is the maximum distance from the Galactic plane) were proposed. Thus, Fig. 4 allows us to visually justify the division of the sample into two kinematically different populations: the main population of the thin disk and a single object with a large eccentricity, probably not associated with this subsystem. Fig. 4 confirms that even among nearby BDs there are objects with extreme kinematic characteristics and, possibly, a special formation history.

Figure 4. Calculated data for the eccentricities from Table 3. The figure from [14] was taken as a basis. Our data for 13 BDs are superimposed on the graph: the red bar in the lower left corner shows the eccentricity range of most of the BDs from our list ($e \approx 0.04 - 0.16$), which fits into the thin disk region. The red circle indicates the Gaia EDR3 ID 1589250088362827776 BD, which stands out for its extreme value $e \approx 0.41$ and $Z_{max} \approx 4.3$ kpc. Its position corresponds to a region typical of halo objects or "hot" representatives of the thick disk.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Based on data from the catalog of [5], a list of BDs located within 10 pc from the Sun was compiled. Of these, 13 objects were identified for which all components of the spatial velocity, including the radial velocity, are known. This made it possible to numerically simulate their orbits within the classical model of the Galaxy using the galpy code. The obtained orbital parameters provide an idea of the dynamic evolution of these objects. Wide binary systems from the WDS catalog were also identified.

1) The distribution of eccentricities of brown dwarfs from our sample demonstrates a narrow range of $e \sim 0.04 \sim 0.16$, which indicates a relatively uniform age of most of the objects and their belonging to the same kinematic subsystem. This may indicate similar conditions of their formation within the "young" thin disk.

2) Most of the BDs rise above the Galactic plane to a height of up to 0.6 kpc, which also indicates that they belong to the thin disk population. This is consistent with the assumption of their relative youth [14], since thin disk stars have almost circular orbits and small oscillations in the Z coordinate.

3) The only exception to the general picture is the brown dwarf with Gaia EDR3 ID 1589250088362827776 (2MASSW J1515008+484742), which exhibits an orbital eccentricity of $e = 0.41$ and reaches a height of $Z_{max} \approx 4.34$ kpc. Such kinematics is typical of halo objects with elongated orbits and high spatial velocities. It is assumed that this BD either belongs to the halo or was dynamically "thrown" into the halo, possibly as a result of the disintegration of a binary system or interaction with massive objects in the Galaxy.

4) The analysis showed that among the nearest BDs, a significant proportion are part of single systems. It was found that the duality does not have a statistically significant effect on the spatial velocities of the BDs,

Table 2. WDS numbers found in SIMBAD for the BDs of our list.

Gaia ID	WDS	x (pc)	y (pc)	z (pc)	U (km/s)	V (km/s)	W (km/s)
5353626573555863424	J10493–5319AB	0.52	–1.92	0.18			
6412596012146801152	J22034–5647Ba,Bb	2.25	–1.00	–2.75			
2794735086363871360	J00363+1821A	–2.92	5.52	–6.10	–40.28	–4.30	–11.82
1227133699053734528	J14164+1348A	3.76	0.21	8.49	–35.92	4.81	–79.39
3303349202364648320	J03554+1134AB	–7.86	0.25	–4.71	–5.43	–26.74	–15.57

Table 3. Results of orbit calculations.

Name	ID Gaia DR3	e	Z_{\max} (kpc)	Comment
WISEPJ180026.60+013453.1	4468009917744160000	0.04396	0.08587	
2MASSWJ1507476–162738	6306068659857135232	0.04833	0.52263	
2MASSJ03552337+1133437	3303349202364648320	0.06916	0.10993	WDS
V488Hya	5753687109122994048	0.07054	0.10497	
2MASSWJ2148162+400359	1954170404122975232	0.07350	0.06133	
2MASSJ06073908+2429574	3426333598021539840	0.09011	0.18601	
LSPMJ0036+1821	2794735086363871360	0.09925	0.06661	WDS
2MASSJ06523073+4710348	954697944875755136	0.10155	0.04453	
2MASSJ18212815+1414010	4485574134969389312	0.10550	0.06700	
2MASSJ17502484–0016151	4371611781971072768	0.11674	0.52088	
2MASSJ14162408+1348263	1227133699053734528	0.14096	1.71010	WDS
CWISEPJ181006.00–101001.1	–	0.15773	0.59646	
2MASSWJ1515008+484742	1589250088362827776	0.40980	4.34173	

but its consideration is important when constructing orbits due to the possible contribution of orbital motion to the measured kinematics.

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¹ <https://www.cosmos.esa.int/gaia>

² <https://www.cosmos.esa.int/web/gaia/dpac/consortium>

³ <http://cds.u-strasbg.fr>